

THE DEVELOPMENT OF LISTENING SKILL IN ENGLISH LANGUAGE

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Abstract: This article highlights some innovative strategies for improving listening skill of English Language of secondary level students. Effective Listening in English language, guiding the students towards effective oral communication, is the problem with all the ESL students at secondary level and as such it creates problem for English language teachers. The objective of the study was to help the English language teachers and students to overcome this problem by showing the results of application of innovative strategies for improving English language listening skill.

Key words: English language teaching, "Art of conversation" program, TEFL, website English club TV innovative strategies, listening comprehension, temptation, language listening skill, challenges, frustrate.

Introduction: Today, listening is the one ability you utilize most frequently in daily life. Your speaking, writing, and reading abilities all start with listening comprehension. It's crucial to actively listen, which involves paying attention to what you're hearing, in order to improve your listening abilities. Make it a habit to watch videos and movies in the foreign language and to listen to audio books, podcasts, news, songs, etc. In this article we can see following listening strategies and their usage: Once you have begun to listen on a regular basis, you might still be frustrated by your limited understanding. Here are a few courses of action you can take:

- accepting the fact that you are not going to understand everything
- keeping a positive attitude when you don't comprehend even if you have problems understanding for a while
- avoid translating into your mother tongue
- focusing on catching the conversation's gist (or main theme). Focus on the major idea first before paying attention to the details

METHODOLOGY

The first problem with translating is that it separates the listener from the speaker. Second, the majority of people frequently repeat themselves. By remaining calm, you can usually understand what the speaker had said. There is a barrier between you and the speaker while you translate. The temptation to instantaneously translate into your mother tongue while hearing someone speak in a foreign language is great. If you hear a term you don't recognize, this temptation intensifies considerably. Naturally, we want to comprehend all that is spoken, therefore this is what happens. However, when you translate into your native language, you are taking the focus of your attention away from the speaker and concentrating on the translation process taking place in your brain. If you could pause the speaker, that would be okay. However, in real life, the other person speaks on while you translate.

RESULTS

This circumstance undoubtedly results in less comprehension, not more. Sometimes, translation causes a mental block in your brain that prevents you from understanding anything at all. Take a time to consider your friends, family, and coworkers. Do they repeat themselves when they speak to you in your language? They probably do if they are typical of most people. If they are like most people, they probably do. Thus, it is highly probable that everyone you listen to will repeat what they just said, allowing you a second, third, or even fourth chance to fully comprehend what they just said. Your brain is free to focus on what is most crucial: understanding English in English if you maintain your composure, are willing to not understand, and refrain from interpreting while you listen. The ability to pick and choose what you want to listen to, how often, and for how long is probably the biggest benefit of using the Internet to develop your listening abilities. You are also very likely to know a lot more of the necessary vocabulary if you listen to something you enjoy. To make the main points easier to understand, use keywords or key phrases. You can infer that someone is talking about a business trip to New York from last year if you understand the words "New York," "business trip," and "last year." This may seem obvious to you, but

remember person continues to speak. Imagine your English-speaking friend telling you, "I got this awesome tuner at JR's. I can now listen to broadcasts on National Public Radio because it was so affordable." You don't understand what a tuner is, and if you focus on the word tuner you might become frustrated. If you think in context, you probably will begin to understand. For example; bought is the past of buy, listen is no problem and radio is obvious. Now you understand: He bought something -- the tuner -- to listen to the radio. A tuner must be a kind of radio.

Even though this is a straightforward illustration, it shows what you should pay attention to-not the terms you don't understand, but rather the ones you do.

DISCUSSION

The most effective technique to develop your listening abilities is to listen frequently. Enjoy the online listening options available and don't forget to unwind. The ability to listen has long been marginalized in foreign language curriculum, despite its evident significance for learning a language. The introduction of teaching communicative languages with an emphasis on competence, learning, and more focus was beginning to be placed on teaching listening. However, listening needs to be given more "prime time" in class and on assignments as it has not yet been fully included into the curriculum. For a variety of reasons, including the following, listening might be difficult for students:

- Listening involves multiple modes:

- Listening involves multiple modes: Interpersonal and interpretive communication are involved in listening. It necessitates that the listener either participate in face-to-face talks or listen in an uninvolved manner while others speak or present.

- Listening involves all varieties of language: In addition to hearing lectures and presentations in formal and academic settings, learners must also participate in or listen to conversations that contain varying degrees of colloquialism

- Listening involves "altered" and "reduced" language forms: Listeners must develop their comprehension of "reduced" language forms in addition to coping with the language's vocabulary and grammatical structures when they are engaged in listening (e.g., I wanna go, Just a sec)

- Variable delivery rates are involved in listening.

Effective skills include the ability to show interest in the subject being addressed and comprehend the data being given. The capacity to communicate effectively is becoming more and more crucial in today's culture. Although the ability to speak effectively is a highly sought after skill, developing effective skills is often not regarded in the same respect. In fact listening is just as important as speaking. Without

learning to be a good listener, you're unlikely achieve understanding. Think about it . Good listening skills will give you an edge in life.

We often think of speaking and writing as the most challenging of the four language skills but what about receptive skills? With reading, learners have time to think, but listening in another language presents a very different set of challenges for the learner. How often have we heard learners' complain " it is too fast teacher"? So how can you help?

Here are some ideas for teachers to try with their learners .

Support every learner

Put a few simple strategies in place in mixed-ability classes to allow the entire class to listen to the same tape and participate in the same activity. As a result, nobody feels left behind or lost among the students.

- Make the gap-filling or sentence makeup work more doable and provide the first letter of any missing words. Alternatively supply the first and the final letter and indicate how many letters the missing word has.

- Provide an additional layer of support for weaker learners by giving them the audioscript. They can read the scripts they listen and use it to help them find the correct answers.

Prepare to listen, Prepare to understand

Don't be in too much of a hurry to hand out the listening task and press "Play". Time spent in class before listening means learners better prepared to understand.

- Before you listen, have a class discussion around the topic of the listening. This gives learners the opportunity not only to practice their speaking but also practice listening to one another. A good discussion will make them think about the main ideas they might hear when they listen.

- Useful vocabulary always comes out of a class discussion, creating very natural way to preteach vocabulary before they listen . Useful language linked to a discussion is easier to learn because learners have context , which makes it easier to remember than preteaching vocabulary from wordlist.

- Take your time to discuss the task and check understanding . Encourage the class to reflect on their discussion and predict the answers. Remember to write their predictions on the board. Did they guess correctly? It doesn't matter if they did or not , what matters is that they are prepared and ready to listen to see if they were right . Feeling prepared to listen means learners feel confident and ready to understand, both in the classroom and exam.

As a rule, listening is one of the most significant component of effective communication in English. Listening is crucial than learning a language as complex as

English especially if one is learning English as a second language. Learning to listen may sound simple and easy at the onset. However, students will soon realise it required considerable mental energy and skill. It is especially true for non-native students learning English as a second language. Proper English listening is a vital requisite of developing speaking skills. The ability to listen to the language and reproduce and imitate those sounds contributes significantly to developing good speaking skills. To develop English listening needs rigorous practice just as one develops muscles in the body.

When improving English listening skills, it is imperative to accept that one is not going to understand everything right from the onset.

The key is not to get discouraged. Perseverance is essential and will deliver the desired results. When listening, one should pay attention to keywords in a spoken sentence. Understanding these keywords will enable the listener to gather the gist of what the speaker is saying. After repetitive listening to the same sentence while knowing its purpose and meaning will help the listener to understand the rest of the words in sentence. The best way to improve one's English listening skills is to seek out resources on the internet. The accessibility and ability to repeatedly watch or listen to such content makes it an ideal source for improving listening skills. One of the best resources is English Club TV. It is a website designed specifically to help non-native speakers learn English. Shows such as "Speak Up" and "Art of Conversation" are ideal source material to improve one's English listening skills.

CONCLUSION

Hearing activities frequently induce high levels of anxiety and stress among learners, which can impede with understanding. Unlike reading texts that can be controlled by the learner, listening texts are continually moving and at varying speeds that are frequently beyond the listener's control. Addressing listening in a language school presents some difficulties for teachers as well. One of your responsibilities as a language instructor will be to create a vision for how listening fits into your classroom. Continue to consider how you may approach listening exercises as you move through this module, as well as the objectives and demands you should have of your students.

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